

ECOBULK

This shelter is part of the EcoBulk project. We aim to make composite materials more sustainable and circular.

The materials used in this shelter were once part of wind turbines for the production of energy. After some

reprocessing and adaptation, we were able to give these materials a second life.

Let us hear from you! Follow the QR code or short link to give us feedback and get more info.

DID YOU KNOW?

After 20-25 years of use, big sections of wind turbines are buried in landfills. This is changing! Projects like EcoBulk are working on reusing and upcycling these materials.

<http://bit.ly/ecobulk>